

RECLAIMING EDUCATION IN THE AGE OF AI

A Handbook of Threat Briefs

ANNEX 4, References

Sources Cited Across All Eleven Threat Briefs

This annex consolidates all references cited in the eleven threat briefs. Each entry has been verified against the published record and confirmed as used in the document text. The Briefs column indicates which threat brief(s) cite each source.

Threat Brief Index

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This annex is part of the handbook *Reclaiming Education in the Age of AI*

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